

TIL TARAQQIYOTI. TIL TARAQQIYOTINING ICHKI QONUNIYATLARI. TILNING TARAQQIYOT BOSQICHLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA. Tilshunoslik fanining predmeti va o'rganish obyekti, uning asosiy tarmoqlari to'g'risida tasavvurni shakllantirish, tilning paydo bo'lishi haqidagi bilimlarni mustahkamlash, til birliklarining o'zaro munosabati haqidagi tushuncha hosil qilish.

Kalit so'zlar: qiyosiy tilshunoslik, xususiy tilshunoslik, turkiy singarmonizmlar.

Qadimgi turkiy til hozirgi barcha turkiy tillar: o'zbek, uyg'ur, qirg'iz, qozoq, turkman, ozarbayjon, usmonli turk, tatar, xakas, yoqut va boshqa tillar uchun qadimgi turkiy til umumiy til, ya'ni bobo til sanaladi. Bu davrda mansub so'zlar: budun-xalq, ingek-sigir, bilig-bilim, yag'i-dushman, yov, batsiq-g'arb, Koch-urug', okush-ko'p, oz-jon, vujud kabilar...

Eski turkiy til X-XII asrlar qoraxoniylar davlati hukm surgan davrdir. Qoraxoniylar davlatida arab tili ilmiy va diniy til bo'lib qoldi, fors-tojik tili rasmiy va adabiy til bo'lsa-da, turkiy tilda ham rasmiy hujjatlar tuzildi. Qoraxoniylar davri adabiy tili hozirgi Markaziy Osiyodagi Barcha turkiy tillarning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi uchun asos bo'lgan til sanaladi. Mahmud Qoshg'ariy tilshunoslik tarixida ilk bor barcha turkiy tillarining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi uchun asos bo'lgan til sanaladi. Mahmud Qoshg'ariy tilshunoslik tarixida ilk bor barcha turkiy tillarning bir necha guruhlarini tasniflab, qiyosiy-tarixiy tilshunoslikka asos soldi. Bu davrga mansub so'zlar: Kokramak-na'ra tortmoq, qirg'ilach-qaldirg'och, sandilach-sa'va, elig-hukmdor, sandug'ach-bulbul, bugu-dono, qut-baraka, emak-mehnat, uma-mehmon. "Devoni lug'oti turk" dan parcha: "Emgak ekinda qolmas"- Mehnat bekorga ketmas, "Uma kelsa, qut kelur"- Mehmon kelsa, Baraka keladi. Eski o'zbek adabiy tilining asoschisi Alisher Navoiy. U o'zbek tilini xazina deb bildi. Bu xazinani ilonlardan va tikanlar o'rab turganini ta'kidladi. U eski o'zbek adabiy tilini ana shu "ilon" va "tikanlar" dan tozalab berdi. Eski o'zbek adabiy tili eng rivojlangan davr XV asr sanaladi. "O'zbek" atamasi tarixda ilk bor Rashididdinning "Mog'ullar tarixi" asarida atoqli ot ma'nosida qo'llangan. Jaloliddin Manguberdining qoshin boshliqlaridan birining ismi O'zbektoy bo'lgan. O'zbek so'zining "o'ziga bek", "otliq qo'shin", "to'g'ri", "sodda", "insofli", "saxiy" kabi ma'nolari bor.

O'zbek atamasining shunga qadar turk, satr, chig'atoy kabi atamalar bilan ishlatilgan. Navoiy davri va Navoiygacha bo'lgan davrda o'zbek tili turk lafzi, turkiy til nomi bilan yuritilgan. XVI asrdan o'zbek urug'larining nomi butun xalqning nomiga aylanib ketdi. Herman Vamberining "Turkiy xalq" asarlarida o'zbek so'zi "o'z" va "bek" so'zlaridan iborat bo'lib, "o'z" so'zining ma'nosi "asl", "ajoyib", "tagi mustahkam", "sardor" degani, xullas "o'zbek" so'zining ma'nosi "aslbek" deb izohlangan. Eski o'zbek adabiy tiliga mansub so'zlar: cherik-lashkar, butradi-tarqadi, ketdi; ev-uy, huvaydo-ayon, ravshan, behbud-sog'lomlik. Tashqi ichki rivojlanish omillari. Lingvistik qonunlar. Tilni rivojlantiruvchi hodisa sifatida tashqi va ichki tilni rivojlantirish omillari.

1. Tildagi ichki o'zgarishlarning sabablari va mexanizmlari
2. Tildagi ichki tarixiy o'zgarishlarning tushuntiriladigan nazariyalari
 - a) Tizimga bosim nazariyasi
 - b) Til probikal rivojlanish nazariyasi
 - c) Innovatsiya nazariyasi
 - d) ziddiyat nazariyasi (antinomiya).

Til ziddiyatlar kompleksini yengib o'tish orqali rivojlanadi:

1. Til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi qarama-qarshilik;
2. Nutq faoliyatida qarama-qarshilik ;
3. Tekshirilgan qarama-qarshiliklar ;

4. Biror kishining ona ommaviy axborot vositalari sifatida qarama-qarshilik deyiladi antinomiya. Tizimni rivojlanishining muayyan bosqichida ruhsat etilgan holda, darhol yana paydo bo'ladi. Antinomiya nazariyasi rus tilida (1968 rus tili va Sovet Jamiyati : zamonaviy rus tilining so'z boyligi) "monografiyasining o'zgarishini tahlil qilishda muvaffiyatli qo'llaniladi. Til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabatlarda qarama-qarshiliklar to'rt antinomiya orqali amalga oshiriladi :

1. Ultratovushda tilni tashkil etuvchi norma talablari natijasida haqiqiy yangilik.
2. Shavqatlilik va ifodali, ular tilni standartlashtirishga qarshi.
3. Til stilistik xilma-xil bo'lishi kerak va intilishlararo so'z boyligining ushbu turiga qarshi.

4. Iqtisodiyot ammo shu bilan bir vaqtning o'zida mo'tadil energiya Tilning rivojlanishi til bo'linmalaridan foydalanishni barqarorlashtirish va buni amalga oshirishga qodir emasligini to'xtatish istagi bilan belgilanadi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik,” og’ir dard,” yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from

<http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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